

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-5, ISSUE-6

METHODS FOR IMPROVING LEARNING OUTCOMES

Bakirova Dilbar Tagayevna

Senior Lecturer, Almalyk Branch of Tashkent State Technical University named after I. Karimov
Phone: +998 50 900 27 12

Jo'rayev Shaxzod No'mon o'g'li

Assistant, Almalyk Branch of Tashkent State Technical University named after I. Karimov
Phone: +998 93 393 99 52

Abduraxmonova Feruza Zafar qizi

Student, Almalyk Branch of Tashkent State Technical University named after I. Karimov
Phone: +998 88 126 11 22

Annotation. This article examines the factors affecting the quality of education, methods of improving the quality of education, redesigning educational institutions, and methods of developing the education system.

Keywords: quality education, model, research, skilled teacher, resource, context, cognitive development, curriculum, etc.

Giving priority to the use of resources in achieving universal, “relevant and effective” education remains a pressing issue.

UNESCO’s International Institute for Educational Planning (IIEP) has conducted numerous studies over the past decade on factors affecting education quality, and developed many models demonstrating their interrelations. At least five such models, seriously discussed at the international level, can be highlighted:

- UNICEF’s 2000 study on education quality
- The 2005 “Education for All” monitoring report
- UNESCO’s General Education Quality Analysis Framework (GEQAF)
- The World Bank’s Systems Approach for Better Education Results (SABER)
- Several well-known international assessments such as PISA

Improving education is a complex task. Below is a summary of **25 methods** for improving the quality of general and secondary education.

25 Ways to Improve Learning Outcomes

Teachers and Pedagogy

1. Distribute highly qualified teachers as equitably as possible across the education system.
2. Improve teacher motivation by enhancing professional status and working conditions.
3. Provide future teachers with real-world job preparation through specialized training and pedagogical practice.
4. Enable teachers to use diverse and context-sensitive pedagogical approaches to meet varied learner needs.
5. Support teachers' continuous professional development through context-specific opportunities without interrupting their work.

Support for Learners

6. Recognize and accommodate the diverse needs and abilities of learners.

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7. Ensure that students of all ages enter school ready to learn—cognitively, physically, and socio-emotionally—and have adequate time for rest, play, and reading.
8. Implement comprehensive early childhood development and home-based learning programs that support parenting skills and holistic child development.
9. Engage parents in promoting and supporting their children's education.
10. Coordinate education with other social services to address socioeconomic disparities affecting student performance.

Curriculum and Learning Materials

11. Teach children in their mother tongue for at least six years before transitioning to another language of instruction.
12. Develop relevant and effective curricula and standards, and ensure their dissemination and implementation.
13. Ensure the availability of appropriate textbooks and teaching guides and that both teachers and students have consistent access to them.
14. Use cost-effective supplementary materials to enrich subject learning and promote the practical application of knowledge.
15. Enhance digital literacy for teachers and students through proper and effective use of ICT tools.

Schools and Resources

16. Train and support top-level administrators who understand how to improve education quality and outcomes and are effective in current management tasks.
17. Redesign classrooms to be open, safe, and comfortable, increasing students' motivation to learn.
18. Implement school-wide policies that promote a positive environment, prevent violence through open communication, ensure reasonable workloads, and foster understanding of the purpose of learning.
19. Ensure that students have adequate time for learning according to planned schedules, improve attendance, teacher motivation, and classroom management.
20. Use diverse assessment methods throughout the year to evaluate learning progress and ensure alignment with quality, validity, and reliability standards.

Education System Management

21. Identify priorities and conduct strategic planning based on reliable data and research to improve learning outcomes.
22. Shift decision-making from centralized to decentralized systems in response to local development needs, ensuring equitable resource distribution.
23. Guarantee transparency and accuracy in institutional reports to enable effective development planning.
24. Develop large-scale monitoring systems to collect reliable data for improving educational environments through systemic changes.
25. Allocate sufficient resources to education and fund institutions that demonstrably improve education quality.

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The issues addressed above apply to general and secondary specialized education systems. However, regarding **higher education**, the following must be noted, as education is seen as a strategic factor in the development of modern society.

At the beginning of the 21st century, scholars emphasized the need to reconsider educational philosophy and develop a new concept of its development in light of global changes. Modernization of society, education, and culture affects the entire higher education system and is only possible within a cultural concept based on innovative principles.

While traditionally established national values remain relevant, they are not effectively realized through the current education system and require internal reform mechanisms [2]. Key drivers of reform in higher education include the needs of the economy, social sectors, science, technology, and innovation. All national and international projects place education sector development at the forefront of their priorities.

Positive changes are also taking place in higher education through the implementation of local networks and global internet connectivity. This has led to the creation of a new educational environment aimed at global informatization of intellectual activity through the use of information technologies.

This environment fosters the development of students' intellectual and creative potential and emphasizes the need for independent learning.

All of this is contributing to fundamental changes in the understanding and evaluation of the individual, giving rise to **new values**. These values must ensure that individuals are free to find their place in the 21st-century world. Such education facilitates intercultural dialogue and opens prospects for a **universal, global education system** that provides genuine human freedom [1].

Like any education system, higher education is characterized by a degree of conservatism. It is important to recognize that no pedagogical paradigm can be implemented without theoretical and methodological foundations and without relying on the accumulated experience of global and national history.

This accumulated experience is the source of both pedagogical ideas and the development of new theories in professional training.

Whether consciously or unconsciously, modern educators are influenced by certain pedagogical trends or ideas, which leads to the emergence of **new educational technologies**. Higher education involves the purposeful training of students. The learning process incorporates both traditional and innovative technologies, and mastering them is a core competency of the higher education instructor. Designing the pedagogical process is essential, regardless of the teacher's experience or readiness to work in higher education.

In conclusion, all the above enables us to speak about the formation of a multicultural society within a modern educational space where students of various ethnolinguistic, religious, and socio-economic backgrounds live and study. This factor must be considered in our multi-ethnic region. Thus, there is every reason to believe that foreign languages play an important **humanitarian, scientific, linguistic, and socio-economic** role in modern society.

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